

THE INFLUENCE OF IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN COMPREHENSIVE SCHOOLS ON IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article talks about improving the management system in general secondary schools and improving the quality of education.*

Keywords: *personnel, family educational institution, educational technology, public, ideological, political, professional level, management system, decrees and decisions, educational process, education of students.*

National personnel training program - implementation of laws on education, implementation of the great tasks set in the reform of the educational system, family educational institution and school, improvement of the quality of education, management and administration of the pedagogical process, activities of the student body establishing and leading the implementation of today's educational technology, involving parents and the public in educational work and being able to establish close cooperation with them are the main tasks of the teacher. The successful solution of these tasks requires raising the ideological, political, and professional level of teacher training. The state policy in the field of the education system envisages the formation of a well-rounded individual citizen through the continuous education system, which is inextricably linked with the intellectual, spiritual and moral education of a person. In this way, one of the most basic constitutional rights of a citizen is realized: the right to acquire knowledge, to show creative ability, to develop intellectually, to work according to one's profession, providing quality education through the standards of vocational education, as well as the choice of forms and types of educational and vocational training, continuous improvement of skills, the right and wide opportunities for appropriate retraining if necessary.

As a consumer of educational services, a person is guaranteed access to state education and vocational training. In the process of education, a person must fulfill the requirements expressed in the state educational standards. As a creator of educational services, after receiving the appropriate qualification level, the person will work in the field of education, material production, science, culture and service. and shares his knowledge and experience in teaching.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev held a meeting on July 17, dedicated to the reform and development of the general secondary education system. The press service of the head of state reported on this. In the following years, decrees and decisions were adopted on the organization of all stages of the education sector based on modern requirements. In accordance with the decision of the head of our state on September 30, 2017, the management system of the Ministry of Public Education was improved, the main tasks and directions of activity were determined.

Recently, changes were made in the leadership of the ministry, and many tasks were set to improve the quality of education by introducing advanced pedagogical and information and

communication technologies into the educational process, raising the status of teachers in society. At the meeting, the measures aimed at reforming the public education system developed on the basis of these instructions were presented. The President gave orders to increase the monthly salary of pedagogues, their position in society, and to support them socially and legally. Limiting the inspections of teachers' activities by various control bodies, beautifying pedagogues, attending meetings, subscriptions and similar professional activities. It was emphasized that one should not be involved in non-essential activities.

The task of establishing a special legal service to protect the rights of teachers was set. President Shavkat Mirziyoev said about this: "It is necessary to raise the quality of general secondary education to a new level. State educational standards and curricula should be revised based on what children need to know in each grade. It is necessary to create and publish textbooks based on the most modern methods, to strengthen the directions of technology, engineering sciences, mathematics, art, and foreign languages in schools, and to re-equip laboratories in this regard. It is also necessary to pay attention to ensuring integration with preschool education and higher education systems.

Reconsidering the demand for principals and deputy principals of general education schools, appointing persons with real managerial skills to this position, deputy principals for moral-educational and educational affairs, etc. It was noted that it is necessary to sharply increase the responsibility. Particular attention was paid to the financing of the public education system. In the formation of the state budget for 2019, it was emphasized that it is expedient to create a special fund under the Ministry of Public Education to increase funding for this sector and to attract highly qualified specialists. An instruction was given on the establishment of a special engineering company in the public education system. Also, the wide introduction of information and communication technologies in the education system, leaving the extra-budgetary income of schools at their disposal, establishing an internal collective control system in schools. In order to increase the number of model schools, attention was paid to issues such as the development of the rating of schools. The reports of the official leaders on the areas discussed at the meeting were heard and relevant tasks were given.

In particular, the following measures are implemented to increase the effectiveness of spiritual, educational and educational activities:

- implementation of five initiatives, which include comprehensive measures aimed at creating additional conditions for youth education, including involving young people in culture and art, physical education and sports, their use of computer and Internet technologies increase literacy, widely promote reading, develop professional skills of girls;

- systematic organization of spiritual and educational work in educational institutions, increasing the effectiveness of the measures implemented in this regard, raising the intellectual potential, thinking and worldview of young people, strengthening their ideological immunity, feeling of patriotism, serving the interests of the people development and implementation of the concept of developing the spiritual and moral consciousness of young people aimed at educating them as a mature generation living with;

- preparing young people who are capable of taking responsibility for solving the important tasks facing the state and society, who are patriotic, enterprising, who have mastered modern knowledge and skills, who have human qualities, as professional professions, which require new approaches in this regard use of educational methods;

-developing and implementing measures to develop sports as a value in educational institutions, popularize a healthy lifestyle among students;

-awareness of the contents of legal documents, development of legal consciousness and culture of young people, observance of a healthy lifestyle, human rights, gender equality, peacekeeping and interethnic harmony, freedom of conscience, languages, customs and traditions of all nations and peoples. development of national and moral values along with universal human values such as respect for mothers, socio-political and economic activity, formation of a strong civic position;

-creating wide conditions for social adaptation of students with disabilities, promoting the ideas of inclusion;

-systematic organization of cooperation of parents, neighborhoods and higher education institutions in youth education;

-to improve the work of sociological and pedagogical-psychological service groups in educational institutions, to prepare students for family life, to strengthen propaganda work on strengthening the family;

-creating conditions in educational institutions for students to learn a trade, acquire new knowledge, work on themselves, purposefully use the achievements of modern technology, and develop entrepreneurial skills;

-effective methods of education, modern information and communication in order to prevent students from falling under the influence of various information attacks, foreign ideas, committing socially dangerous acts by them, and uniting them towards the future of our country wide use of technologies, taking into account their interest in organizing spiritual and educational events and supporting their initiatives;

Within the framework of the concept "School is a center of spirituality and enlightenment", formation of spiritual and educational worldview of students and young people, improvement of legal literacy, path to profession. Great attention was paid to the development of cooperation based on the mentoring model in matters such as education and preparation for independent life.

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